

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: (Site) N-S

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions: _____

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) 5-10 cm Medium (range) 10-15 cm Large (range) 20-30 cm Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing: **NONE**

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type: _____

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: Length 120cm, width 58cm, only 14cm height as excavated

Description: Small wall of irregular tufo stones, some worked on (only) one side to present a flatter facade. Wall is cut by SU 1436 to the north.

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1453 is a small partial wall just to the east of the entrance to the house in area B. It appears to match, in construction technique + rough alignment, wall SU 1450 to the south. The two are separated by a gap of ca. 90cm, which may represent a threshold for the entrance to room 6; however, the orientation of wall SU 1453 appears to curve slightly to the east in relation to that of SU 1450. To the north this wall is cut by SU 1436, so its relationship to the other walls in this area is uncertain.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by S.FARR

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